

Research Article

Effects of nitrogen application on dry land wheat roots and shoot

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ABSTRACT

Nitrogen application could have affected the shoot and roots of plants. This experiment was conducted in a split plot design with ten nitrogen levels (0, 15, 20, 30, 40, 45, 60, 80, 90 and 120 kg N.ha⁻¹ as urea) in main plot and 5 dry land wheat genotypes (Azar2, Sardari, Sardari39, Sardari101 and Rasad) in sub-plot with 4 replications. Results showed that, in tillering stage (GS21) nitrogen fall application increased plant wet weight, root wet weight significantly at 1%, and increased number of nodal roots, plant dry weight and root volume significantly at 5%. Nitrogen application increased root wet weight 157%, root volume 114%, number of nodal roots 60% and grain yield 47%. Results showed that root wet weight, root volume and number of nodal roots was significantly positive maximum direct effects on grain yield respectively. Coleoptile, root wet weight and seminal roots length were affected indirectly above the mentioned characteristic effects on grain yield. Direct effects of coleoptile length, seminal roots length and number of seminal roots were negative on grain yield significantly. Mean dry-land wheat nitrogen requirement for obtaining of 95% maximum grain yield and maximum root volume, calculated 42 kgN.ha⁻¹ from urea in drought year with 137 mm annual rainfall.

Keywords:

Nitrogen, root, shoot, dry land, wheat.

Introduction

Production of wheat in arid and semiarid area is greatly dependent on nitrogen management. In this area, nitrogen is the most limited plant nutrient because of low soil organic matter. Therefore, nitrogen mineralization is not sufficient for cereal nitrogen requirement and optimal nitrogen application are vital for increasing wheat yields in these areas (Ryan, 2002; Ryan et al, 2008). The root of plants has a great effect on the cereals resistance in environmental stress. Characteristics of root such as: growth rate to depth and maximum rooting depth indicate the potential, of available mineral nitrogen and water supplementation in subsoil for crops (Svoboda et al, 2000; King et al, 2003). While mineral N in densely rooted topsoil and shallow subsoil (40–50 cm) is available, uptake of nitrogen and water from sparsely rooted subsoil may be limited by the rate of ion transport to root surface. Thus, any management practices which have direct or indirect effect on root density in subsoil may change the ability of a crop to deplete deep soil horizons. A concern exists that, high doses of nitrogen decrease growth to depth and root density in subsoil, as crops demand for N that is saturated from enriched topsoil layer. It was reported that wheat and other cereals cultivated hydroponically or in pot and field experiments by increasing nitrogen supply, enhanced both shoot and root growth, but usually shoot growth more than root growth, leading to increased shoot/root dry weight ratio with increase N supply (Marschner, 1995; Lucas et al, 2000). At high N rates, inhibition of root mass and root length was observed (Svoboda and Haberle, 2006). N fertilizer is affected by number and length of seminal and nodal roots in wheat (Herrera, J.M, 2007). The results of the field experiment by Svoboda and Haberle (2006) showed that 100 kg. ha⁻¹ of N fertilization did not significantly affect root depth and root length in the soil profile while a high rate N. of 200 kg ha⁻¹ - reduced root growth in subsoil in some years. The objective of this study was to determine the effect of nitrogen fertilization on dry-land wheat genotypes root.

Material and Methods

This study was conducted in a split plot design in randomized complete block, with ten nitrogen rates in fall including (0, 15, 20, 30, 40, 45, 60, 80, 90 and 120 kg N.ha⁻¹ from urea) as the main plot and five dry-land wheat genotypes -Azar2, Sardari, Sardari 39, Sardari 101 and Rasad- as the subplot with 4 replications in Maragheh Dryland Agricultural Research Institute (DARI) station in the year of 2007-2008. The soil of the field experiment

was a clay loam (Fine Mixed Active Mesic Typic Calcixerents). Combined soil sampling before wheat cultivation derived from (0-25 Cm) depth and its general soil (chemical and physical) analysis measured in laboratory (Table 1). Rainfall for this growing season was 137.6 mm, 245.7 mm lower than the 10 years average (Table 2). The plots were sown in fall 2007 at a seed rate of 400 seeds per m² in depth of 5-7 cm.

Nitrogen rates replaced under seed bed in fall contemporary with winter wheat genotypes cultivation. For studding root in tillering growth stage (GS21) according to codding Zadoks et al (1974) until defined depth (30 Cm) used from cylindrical tubes (with 20 Cm diameter). Cylindrical tubes were replaced on cultivation row in proper soil moisture time. Then, plant samples were gathered from plots and stored at 5°C and as soon as possible, the roots were washed to be free of soil on a sieve with 3 mm apertures (Smuker, A.J. 1984; Svoboda and Haberle, 2006) and then the whole roots and shoots are separated from each other. Lastly the root and shoot characteristics were studied, and statistical analysis of total data from this project carried out with Genstat software.

Results

Roots:

The effects of nitrogen treatment was significant on root wet weights ($P < 0.01$) and number of nodal roots. Root volume significantly at ($P < 0.05$) was affected by treatments (Table 3). The highest root wet weight 0.44 gr.plant⁻¹ present for 90 Kg N. ha⁻¹ and the lowest root wet weight 0.14 gr.plant⁻¹ obtained from control treatment. Mean comparison of root characteristics for nitrogen treatments in tillering stage indicated that the highest number of nodal roots 3.53 presents for 80 Kg.ha⁻¹ N and the lowest number of nodal roots 2.2 obtained from control treatment. The results shows that the highest root volume 0.403 cm³.plant⁻¹ present for 90 Kg N.ha⁻¹ treatment and the lowest root volume 0.165 cm³.plant⁻¹ obtained from control treatment.

The effects of genotype only was significant ($P < 0.01$) on number of nodal roots and was significant ($P < 0.05$) on number of seminal roots (Table 3). Among the wheat genotypes in Tillering stage, mean number and length of seminal roots was more than mean nodal roots respectively 45% and 69% (table 5). Highest mean number of seminal roots 4.67 present for Sardari genotype and the lowest mean number of seminal roots 4.28 belong to Azar 2. Also, results shown that the highest mean number of nodal roots 3.5 present for Sardari 101 genotype, and the lowest mean number of nodal roots 2.92 obtained from Sardari variety. The mean number of nodal roots of Sardari 101 was 19% higher than Sardari and 16% higher than the other genotypes.

Shoots:

The effects of nitrogen treatment was significant on shoot wet weight ($P < 0.01$) and shoot dry weight at ($P < 0.05$) (Table 3). The highest shoot wet weight 1.28 gr.plant⁻¹ present for 80 Kg N.ha⁻¹ treatment and the lowest shoot wet weight 0.53 gr.plant⁻¹ obtained from control treatment. Whereas the highest shoot dry weight 0.177 gr.plant⁻¹ present for 80 Kg N.ha⁻¹ treatment and

the lowest shoot dry weight 0.089 gr.plant⁻¹ obtained from control treatment.

The effects of genotype was significant ($P < 0.05$) on Shoot dry weight. The highest mean shoot dry weight 0.155gr.plant⁻¹ was present for Sardari 101 genotype and the lowest mean shoot dry weight 0.155 gr.plant⁻¹ obtained from Sardari cultivar (Table 5).

Calculation of Shoot/root ratio showed that this ratio affected by nitrogen application. Fig1 indicate that this ratio until 80 Kg.ha⁻¹ has increasing trend but up to N₈₀ was vice versa to N₁₂₀.

Path analysis

Showed that, root wet weight, root volume and number of nodal roots was significantly positive maximum direct effects on grain yield respectively and by increasing these characteristics, grain yield has increasing trend. Study of indirect effects showed that, indirect effects of Coleoptil length were significantly negative decreased direct effects of root wet weight in total correlation but

indirect effects of root volume on direct effects of root wet weight was positive and not significant. Also, indirect effects of Coleoptil length decreased direct effects of root volume on grain yield but this negative effect in total correlation was repaired by effects of root wet weight on root volume. However direct effects of number of nodal roots was affected by the grain yield of dry land wheat significantly and positively, but indirect effects of seminal roots length were decreased correlation between number of nodal roots and grain yield and this relation has no significant (Table 6).

Study of direct effects of characteristics showed that effects of Coleoptil length, seminal roots length and number of seminal roots on grain yield were significant and negative. Indirect effects of root wet weight has could converted negative and real effects of Coleoptil length on grain yield in total correlation to positive, whereas such logical relation was not seen between Coleoptil length and grain yield (Table 6). At last, the real effects of root characteristics for increasing grain yield respectively are:

> Root wet weight	> Root volume	Number of nodal roots
High effect	Moderate effect	Low effect

N fertilizer recommendation

The results of regression analysis showed that mean dry-land wheat nitrogen requirement for obtaining of

95% maximum grain yield and maximum root volume, calculated 42 kg N.ha⁻¹ from urea in drought year with 137 mm annual rainfall (fig 2).

Table 1: Mean of physical and chemical characteristics of the experimental field before experiment performance.

Depth (cm)	Sand	Silt	Clay	pH	EC (dS.m ⁻¹)	SP	TNV (%)	O.C
0-20	23	29	48	7.5	0.46	71	1.8	0.04
20-40	28	31	41	7.7	0.46	63	5.8	0.41
40-60	21	31	48	7.7	0.44	78	11.3	0.02
60-80	25	32	43	7.8	0.39	75	16.0	0.12
80-100	48	25	27	7.7	0.63	73	14.5	0.02

Continuation of Table 1.

NO ₃ ⁻	NH ₄ ⁺	P	K	Fe	Mn	Zn	Cu
(mg.kg ⁻¹)							
5.6	5.6	18.1	460	8.5	2.18	1.6	2.2
2.8	2.8	1.6	310	6.1	1.82	0.5	2.0
5.6	4.2	1.3	250	6.0	1.52	0.8	1.7
7.0	4.2	1.2	210	5.0	1.06	0.6	1.0
19.6	8.4	2.0	150	4.0	0.66	2.7	0.6

Table 2: The average temperature and Precipitation in mean 10 years and in 2007-2008 in Maragheh Dryland Agricultural Research Institute (DARI)

Year	Evaporation	Precipitation	Mean relative moisture	Zero number day	Mean temperature	Mean maximum temperature	Mean minimum temperature
		(mm)	(%)			(°C)	
10 years average	1798.8	383.3	47.5	140	10.1	15.9	4.8
2007-2008	1324	137.6	43.22	118	6.7	11.861	1.57

Fig 1: Relation between rate of nitrogen application and shoot/root ratio in tillering stage.

Fig 2: Relation between nitrogen treatments, grain yield, volume of wheat root in tillering stage

Table 3: Analysis of variance for root and shoot characteristics in tillering stage

S.O.V	d.f	Mean Square									
		Seminal root number	Nodal root number	Nodal root length	Seminal root length	Coleoptil length	Shoot wet weight	Root wet weight	Root dry weight	Shoot dry weight	Root volume
Replication	1	1.099 ns	4.63nns	1.364 ns	23.16 ns	1.042 ns	1.123 ns	0.0002 ns	0.0002 ns	0.062 ns	0.0116 ns
Nitrogen	9	0.158 ns	1.469n*	6.118 ns	3.126 ns	0.429 ns	0.443**	0.0572**	0.0062 ns	0.0063*	0.042 *
Residual	9	0.143	0.401	3.935	3.101	0.467	0.066	0.0082	0.0035	0.0014	0.0097
Genotype	4	0.529 *	1.095 **	0.682 ns	0.407 ns	0.276 ns	0.071 ns	0.0123 ns	0.01 ns	0.0017*	0.01344 ns
Nitrogen×Genotype	36	0.197 ns	0.26 ns	3.18	3.182 ns	0.333 ns	0.028 ns	0.0124 ns	0.0047 ns	0.005 ns	0.0109 ns
Residual	120	0.185	0.304	3.987 ns	3.238	0.222	0.037	0.0111	0.0059	0.0008	0.0091
CV (%)	-	9.6	17.7	20.5	10.9	12.4	19.8	34.2	150.4	19.3	30.6

Ns,*and ** respectively non significant, P<0.05 and P<0.01

Table 4: Mean comparison for different nitrogen treatment for root and shoot characteristics in tillering stage

Nitrogen (Kg/ha)	Seminal root number	Nodal root number	Nodal root length (Cm)	Seminal root length (Cm)	Coleoptil length (Cm)	Shoot wet weight (gr/plant)	Root wet weight (gr/plant)	Root dry weight (gr/plant)	Shoot dry weight (gr/plant)	Root volume (Cm ³ /plant)
0 (Control)	4.37 a	2.2 c	8.4 a	15.6 a	3.99 a	0.53 e	0.14 e	0.024 a	0.089 e	0.165 d
15	4.4 a	3.06 ab	8.6 a	16.6 a	3.76 a	0.81 d	0.27 d	0.097 a	0.136 cd	0.262 c
20	4.57 a	3.3 a	9.4 a	17.1 a	3.77 a	0.92 cd	0.34 bc	0.078 a	0.136 cd	0.3 bc
30	4.36 a	3.11 ab	9.6 a	16.7 a	3.88 a	0.95 cd	0.36 b	0.039 a	0.144 cd	0.353 ab
40	4.52 a	3.4 a	10.6 a	16.2 a	3.77 a	1.05 bc	0.3 bcd	0.037 a	0.146 cd	0.316 bc
45	4.78 a	2.77 b	10.4 a	16.1 a	4.29 a	0.9 cd	0.29 cd	0.033 a	0.128 d	0.298 bc
60	4.59 a	3.24 a	10.4 a	16.8 a	3.67 a	1.04 bc	0.33 bcd	0.039 a	0.148 bcd	0.343 ab
80	4.45 a	3.53 a	10.6 a	16.3 a	3.6 a	1.28 a	0.03 bcd	0.043 a	0.177 a	0.337 ab
90	4.42 a	3.2 ab	9.5 a	16 a	3.61 a	1.2 ab	0.44 a	0.084 a	0.173 ab	0.403 a
120	4.49 a	3.33 a	10.1	16.5 a	3.75 a	1.07 bc	0.32 bc	0.038 a	0.161 abc	0.332 bc
LSD 5%	0.38	0.64	2	1.8	0.69	0.26	0.09	0.06	0.037	0.1

Table 5: Mean comparison for dryland wheat genotypes different for root and shoot characteristics in tillering stage

Genotypes	Seminal root number	Nodal root number	Nodal root length	Seminal root length	Coleoptil length	Shoot wet weight	Root wet weight	Root dry weight	Shoot dry weight	Root volume
Azar 2	4.28 b	2.96 b	9.61 a	16.44 a	3.63 a	1.01 a	0.312 a	0.077 a	0.149 a	0.297 a
Sardari	4.67 a	2.92 b	9.86 a	16.49 a	3.95 a	0.93 a	0.284 a	0.033 a	0.134 b	0.298 a
Sardari 39	4.44 b	3.16 b	9.99 a	16.37 a	3.79 a	1 a	0.293 a	0.035 a	0.147 ab	0.303 a
Sardari 101	4.65 a	3.5 a	9.74 a	16.75 a	3.82 a	1.04 a	0.348 a	0.074 a	0.155 a	0.357 a
Rasad	4.44 b	3.03 b	9.53 a	16.64 a	3.85 a	0.9 a	0.305 a	0.037 a	0.135 b	0.299 a
LSD5%	0.28	0.35	1.28	1.15	0.3	0.12	0.067	0.049	0.018	0.061

Table 6: Direct and indirect effects of root characteristics on dryland wheat grain yield in tillering stage (GS21)

Characteristics	Direct effects	Indirect effects								total correlation
		number of seminal roots	Number of Nodal roots	Nodal root length	Seminal root length	Seminal root length	Root wet weight	Root dry weight	Root volume	
number of seminal roots	-1.448 ns	-	-0.158 ns	2.21 **	0.054 ns	0.12 ns	0.087 ns	-0.368 ns	0.084 ns	0.404 ns
Number of Nodal roots	-2.382 ns	-0.096 ns	-	2.45 **	0.268 ns	-0.16 ns	0.561 ns	0.475 ns	-0.542 ns	0.574 ns
Nodal root length	3.876 ns	-0.821 **	-1.505 **	-	0.098 ns	-0.023 ns	0.318 ns	-0.692 *	-0.425 ns	0.821 **
Seminal root length	0.469 ns	-0.168 ns	-1.362 **	0.809 **	-	-0.073 ns	0.301 ns	0.296 ns	-0.246 ns	0.028 ns
Seminal root length	0.235 ns	-0.738*	1.62 **	-0.378 ns	-0.142 ns	-	-0.367 ns	-0.703*	0.341 ns	-0.133 ns
Root wet weight	0.821 ns	-0.138 ns	-1.628 **	1.5 **	0.172 ns	-0.105 ns	-	0.724*	-0.675 *	0.67 *
Root dry weight	1.67 ns	-0.319 ns	-0.677 *	-1.606 **	0.083 ns	-0.099 ns	0.356 ns	-	-0.159 ns	-0.114 ns
Root volume	-0.71 ns	-0.172 ns	-1.818 **	2.319 **	0.162 ns	-0.113 ns	0.78 **	0.373 ns	-	0.821 **

CONCLUSIONS

This study was carried out in drought year (137<mm rain fall) and Nitrogen application could increase grain in yield. Root studies showed that application of high amount N under dry land conditions could increase number of nodal roots and capable plant to better water and nutrient absorption from soil. Nodal roots depend largely on environmental factors such as nutrient availability more than seminal roots. However, the soil type and its physical conditions and chemical properties, together with the climate and management practices can ally modify the number, growth and distribution of nodal roots. This characteristic was different between wheat cultivars. Shoot wet weight had highly increased and caused shoot/root ratio. Although root growth was relatively lower than shoot growth by nitrogen application but greater production of finer branch roots increased nutrient availability (Welbank et al, 1974; Li et al, 1999). Fall nitrogen application (80 Kg.ha⁻¹) in this project increased shoot dry weight 98% (table 4). This is in agreement to results of Feiziasl et al (2005) and Halverson (2004).

In this study, fall application of 90 Kg N.ha⁻¹ increased root volume 144% in respect to control. Whereas increasing amount of nitrogen applied more than 90 Kg.ha⁻¹ inhibited root volume increasing trend. Just like this study (Hodge, 2004) reported, that low rate of N application increase root volume but high amount of N application decrease root volume.

In this investigation the highest number of seminal and nodal roots was obtained from sardari and sardari 101 genotypes respectively. Also, there were differences in the distribution of roots among the varieties and nitrogen levels. Perusal of data revealed that rates of N fertilization may not change root length density, but varietal effects on root growth such as root wet weight, root volume and number of nodal roots are linked to patterns of grain yield formation of wheat in dry land conditions.

In drought conditions such as in this study, increasing the supply of nitrogen in the rooting zone tend to decrease the proportion of photosynthate invested in roots relative to that in the shoot and nitrogen application increased shoot/root ratio. Mineral N suppressed photo-assimilate partitioning to roots and increased it to above ground organs (Anderson et al, 2005). By such mechanisms increased water use efficiency. These results also suggest that fall nitrogen application in water deficit conditions (such as dry land farming areas) increase tolerance of plants to stress and increase the economical yield.

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